

**XVI SPANISH-PORTUGUESE SYMPOSIUM
ON PLANT WATER RELATIONS
NEW SOLUTIONS FOR ANCIENT CHALLENGES**
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Enhancing Maize (*Zea mays*) Resilience to Drought Stress Through Seed-Associated Microbiota

Inês Rebelo Romão¹, Tatiana Gil¹, Lucas Amoroso Lopes de Carvalho^{1,2}, Joana do Carmo Gomes¹, Andre Sousa¹, Sara Mateus¹, Raquel Teixeira¹, Flavia Kasa¹, and Juan Ignacio Vílchez^{1*}

*Correspondence: nacho.vilchez@itqb.unl.pt

¹ Instituto de Tecnologia Química e Biológica (ITQB)-NOVA, iPlantMicro Lab. Oeiras, Lisboa, Portugal.

² Laboratory of Bioinformatics, Department of Agricultural, Livestock and Environmental Biotechnology, School of Agricultural and Veterinary Sciences, São Paulo State University (UNESP), Jaboticabal, SP, 14884-900, Brazil.

Abstract: Drought stress poses a significant challenge for global maize production, with far-reaching impacts on livelihood and economy. As climate change intensifies, the frequency of unpredictable weather events is expected to rise, with the need of adaptative strategies. Endophytic microorganisms are selectively recruited by the plant to cope with a diversity of stresses and conditions, being able to enter the plant through vertical inheritance from the parental line. Our project focuses on the selection of novel bioinoculants, with an innovative approach directed towards seed-associated microbiota. The rationale behind this approach lies in the capacity of seed microbiota to be influenced and selected by parental lines, thereby shaping the performance of future generations. Using the widely-grown SY Carioca maize variety, we isolated, identified and characterized its seedborne microbiota by *in vitro* tests, and under greenhouse conditions as inoculants. The strains were applied as single treatment and different irrigation percentages (25%, 50% and 100%) were applied. The greenhouse results indicate that seedborne bacteria are able to promote the growth of maize seedlings, and two of them, *Burkholderia ubonensis* JC and *Pseudomonas fluvi* MB showed a high protection level of the seedlings under water-restrictive conditions. After this screening, the strain *Pseudomonas fluvi* MB was selected as the best candidate to proceed with a future characterization as biotreatment on to field trials. These results offer a promising path towards the development of more eco-friendly and efficient solutions to enhance maize resilience against drought stress, ultimately contributing to sustainable agriculture in an era of evolving climate challenges.

Keywords: seedborne microbiota, drought mitigation, corn productivity, abiotic stress

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1. Introduction

Maize (*Zea mays* L.) is one of the most relevant crops, but the production is affected by high temperatures and droughts (Khatibi et al., 2022). These phenomena are increasingly observed, causing 20-40% of losses in the Iberian Peninsula (Toreti et al., 2023). Despite de breeding programs and the efficient use of water, the climatic perspective is requiring a broader perspective to alleviate negative effects. Consequently, the implementation of treatments based on microorganisms represents alternative to improve the drought tolerance in corps (Mubeen et al., 2021). These microorganisms show capabilities as 1-aminocyclopropane-1-carboxylate deaminase, biofilms or auxin production (Gamalero and Glick, 2022). Most of them has been isolated in the rhizosphere, but more recently seed microbiota emerged as a more efficient alternative. This population reflects how the parental line has adapted to environmental stresses, so they could suppose a pre-selected kind of drought treatment (Mascot-Gómez et al., 2021). This work seeks to explore the potential use of maize seedborne bacteria as a new treatment against drought effects. For this, we have evaluated their key features under regular and stressful conditions to enhance the integration of these treatments as biotechnological applications.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1 Plant material and seedborne microbiota characterization

Maize seeds (*Zea mays* L.) of the variety SY Carioca were kindly borrowed by Anpromis Association (Portugal). About 50 seeds were surface-sterilized with 70% ethanol for 5 minutes, and washed with sterile, double distilled water (Vilchez et al., 2021). They were then germinated in Magenta boxes in darkness at 28 °C, and then three 3-cm length roots were grounded, diluted in sterile NaCl 0.45% solution and dispersed in LB agar plates to quantify the culturable populations. Distinguishable colonies were isolated and pure cultures were identified by PCR amplification of the 16S rRNA gene, as previously optimized in our laboratory for seedborne microbiota (Niza-Costa et al., 2022). The core, resilient microbiota was described and the isolates were glycerol-preserved at -80 °C. The strains were evaluated under regular conditions and supplemented by 15% polyethylene glycol (PEG) as drought-mimicking agent. Thereafter, they were characterized as able to grow in 1-aminocyclopropane-1-carboxylate (ACC) medium as indication of ACC deaminase production, and to produce biofilm and auxins, as previously optimized and tested in our lab for high-throughput, spectrophotometric tests (Niza Costa et al., 2023). Finally, the colonization rate of the candidates was assessed by *in vitro* tests, according to Vilchez and collaborators (Vilchez et al., 2021).

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2.3 Greenhouse test

The best candidates were prepared as liquid inoculants (10^8 colony forming units/mL in 0.45% NaCl solution) to treat 2-days-old seedlings in 0.5 L pots filled with turf and vermiculite (3:1, v:v). After treatment, irrigation regimes of 100%, 50% and 25% were applied (Vílchez et al., 2016). Then, 14 days after treatment (DAT), height, root length, dry weight (DW) and photosystem II quantum yield were evaluated (FluorPen FP110).

3. Results

The most resilient population (core microbiota) was composed by *Paenibacillus endophyticus* JA (24.2%), *Pseudomonas fulva* MB (21.9%), *Paenibacillus silvae* JB (17.2%), *Stenotrophomonas indicatrix* MD (14.8%), *Stenotrophomonas maltophilia* MC (9.1%), *Pseudomonas koreensis* MA (4.9%) and *Burkholderia ubonensis* JC (3.1%). Other bacteria less represented (<3%) were not considered for further testing (Fig. 1a). On the other hand, the growth of the strains JA, JC, MA and MB in ACC medium under stress was maintained (Fig. 1b). In the case of biofilm production (Fig. 1c), under stressful conditions, strains JA, JC and MC kept the performance, and the strain MB even increased by 15%. Finally, JC and MC produced similar amount of auxin under stress, and the strain MB increased by 68% (Fig. d).

Figure 1. Characterization of the seedborne population in maize. The pie chart (a) shows the relative abundance of isolated strains. The bar graphs show the ACCd (b), biofilm (c) and auxins (d) production. Graphs in green and red indicate regular and +15%PEG conditions, respectively. The * stands for significant difference at least $p < 0.05$ respect to regular conditions. The codenames in the graphs stand for *P. endophyticus* JA, *P. silvae* JB, *B. ubonensis* JC, *P. koreensis* MA, *P. fulva* MB, *S. maltophilia* MC, *S. indicatrix* MD, *Bacillus pumilis* A, *B. safensis* WC, *B. zhangzhouensis* C, *Stenotrophomonas chelatiphaga* YC, *Pseudomonas oryzihabitans* CC, *Paenibacillus humicus* WT, *B. amyloliquefaciens* B, *P. polymyxa* D, and *Chryseobacterium* sp. E.

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Considering the test on seedlings, the colonization ratio was generally reduced under stress, but with the strains MC and MD this was a moderate 15-25%. In the case of the strain MB, no significant reduction was recorded (Fig. 2a). Thus, the strains JA, JC and MB were selected as the best candidates for the greenhouse inoculation test. Here, all the treatment improved plant status under 100% irrigation, but only the one with JC and MB improved seedlings resistance to limited irrigation regimes (Fig. 2b). This tendency is well represented in height, dry weight and photosystem II quantum yield, where a more and more restrictive water regime decreased the parameters in general, maintaining JC and MB treatment better values in physiological and seedling health parameters, respectively. The strain JA showed no difference respect to the mock set under restrictive irrigation regimes, with same clear visual and photosystem II quantum yield wilting status. Interestingly, mid irrigation regime increased root length in the all seedlings treated with the candidate strains. However, under no irrigation, the seedlings treated with JA showed a critical reduction in this parameter. The strain MB stood out over JC in most of the parameters evaluated.

Figure 2. Plant testing of candidate strains. The graph bar (a) shows the colonization ratio in regular (green) and stressing conditions (+15%PEG; red). relative abundance of isolated strains. The * stands for significative difference at least $p < 0.05$ respect to regular conditions. The pictures (b) show the status of the seedling after inoculation with the candidate strains under different water regimes. Finally, the bar graphs in the lower panels show the height (c), root length (d), dry weight (e) and photosystem I quantum yield (f) registered for the greenhouse inoculation experiment. Here, columns in green, yellow and red indicate 100%, 50% and 25% regular and +15%PEG conditions, respectively. The codenames in the graphs stand for *P. endophyticus* JA, *P. sylvae* JB, *B. ubonensis* JC, *P. koreensis* MA, *P. fulva* MB, *S. maltophilia* MC, *S. indicatrix* MD.

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4. Discussion

Nowadays, the agriculture is facing the challenge of extreme climate conditions, as well as the necessity to reduce fertilizers and other inputs. The use of new biotreatments may suppose a sustainable alternative to improve plant growth and response to stresses as drought (Kumar et al., 2022). Here, the use of seed microbiota emerges as a tailor-made and more efficient approach (Abdelfattah et al., 2023). Many new studies are addressing this option, this still a very unexplored field, which still requires to understand core populations, mechanism or application reliability. In our study, despite several other *Pseudomonas* has been characterized as plant growth-promoting bacteria, to our knowledge, we have characterized for the first time the of a seedborne *Pseudomonas fulva* strain as efficient biotreatment as a plant drought-tolerance enhancer (Yasmin et al., 2022). This strains has been used previously in maize a consortium to improve biocontrol effect on *Fusarium* sp. (Adeniji and Babalola, 2022). The utilization of seed microbiota create new alternatives for the biotreatments use as they provide pre-adapted strains that could consist in better results, especially if we consider the local-sourced and climate-adapted ones (contextualized use) (Bziuk et al., 2021). However, aspects as consortia use, minimal core microbiota by species/genotypes to consider or stress-specific inheritance need to be discerned to guarantee the future design of products (Abdelfattah et al., 2023). Finally, our model in maize was promising, but it's necessary to check under field conditions, as well as the putative interspecific use of the strains here characterized in order to better understand these types of interactions and potential industrial applications (Simonin et al., 2022).

5. Conclusion

The maize seed population evaluate has high variation, but hold a core microbiota consisting in species from the genera *Paenibacillus*, *Burkholderia*, *Stenotrophomonas* and *Pseudomonas*. Most of them were able to produce auxins, biofilms and ACC deaminase, even under stressing conditions. The strains *Paenibacillus endophyticus* JA, *Burkholderia ubonensis* JC, and *Pseudomonas fulva* MB improved plant growth, but only JC and MB enhanced maize seedlings response to water restriction. *Pseudomonas fulva* MB stood out and may suppose a new seed-isolated strain employed as field biotreatment against drought effects.

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